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MEDICINAL PROPERTIES AND PHYTOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF CAPPARIS SPINOSA L.

BEGMATOVA MALOKHAT KHUSHVAKTOVNA

Associate professor of Samarkand State university of veterinary medicine, animal husbandry and biotechnology

ABDISALOMOVA, MOHINUR DAUGHTER OF ABDIMUROD

Graduate student of Samarkand state university of veterinary medicine, animal husbandry and biotechnology

Annotatsiya. Bugungi kunda dunyo bo'yicha farmatsevtika korxonalarida ishlab chiqarilayotgan dori vositalarining taxminan 50% dorivor o'simliklar xomashyosidan tayyorlanmoqda. Ko'pchilik mamlakatlarda, shu jumladan, O'zbekiston Respublikasida farmatsevtika sanoatini jadallik bilan rivojlanishi bunday korxonalarining dorivor o'simliklar xomashyosiga bo'lgan talabni keskin ortishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Shunday ekan tabiiy holda o'suvchi dorivor o'simliklar zaxiralarining chegaralanganligi tufayli farmatsevtika sanoati korxonalarining dorivor o'simliklar xomashyosiga bo'lgan talabini, dorivor o'simliklar yetishtirish orqali qondirish bugungi kunning asosiy vazifalaridan biridir. Ana shunday o'simliklardan biri Capparis spinosa l.

Resume. Today, approximately 50% of the drugs produced in pharmaceutical enterprises around the world are made from raw medicinal plants. The rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry in many countries, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, causes a sharp increase in the demand for medicinal plant raw materials from such enterprises. Therefore, due to the limited resources of naturally growing medicinal plants, it is one of the main tasks of today to meet the demand of the pharmaceutical industry enterprises for the raw materials of medicinal plants through the cultivation of medicinal plants. One such plant is Capparis spinosa l.

Kalit so'zlar. O'simlik, xomashyo, fitomassasi, ildizi, po'stlog'i, bargi, guli, fitomassa, maxsuldorlik, generativ novdalar, vegetativ novda, dag'al poya, tuproq-iqlim sharoitlari.

Keywords. Plant, juice, phytomass, root, bark, leaf, flower, phytomass, productivity, generative branches, vegetative stem, grayish stem, soil and climatic conditions.

Enter. As we know, the properties of medicinal plants were known in ancient times. Written 5,000 years before our era, Sien Jun's anthology contains information about 230 types of medicinal and poisonous plants known to the ancient Chinese.

The first works on medicinal plants were written by the ancient Greek physician Hippocrates (460-377). He wrote down information about more than 200 medicinal plants known in the medicine of that time.

Scholars of the East, Abu Abdullah Muhammad Ibn Musa Al-Khorazmi, Abu Bakr Muhammad Ibn Ahmad Zakaria, Abul Ghazi Khan, son of Arab Muhammad

Khan, and Abu Mansur Bukhari also made a great contribution to the development of medical science.

The great scientist Abu Ali Ibn Sina wrote about the healing properties of more than 400 plants and their methods of use in his book "Kitab al-Qanun fit-tib" "Laws of Medicine".

PF-5707 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 10.04.2019 According to the decree "On measures for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2019-2021" in the following years, the population of the republic will be provided with medicines, medical supplies and medical equipment (hereinafter referred to as pharmaceutical products) complex measures were implemented to improve the system, favorable conditions were created for the development of the local pharmaceutical network.

At the same time, insufficient production capacity and a narrow range of domestic pharmaceutical products do not meet the needs of the domestic market and lead to excessive dependence on imports.

In the implementation of these tasks, it is of great scientific importance to substantiate the biological properties of essential oils and medicinal plants containing monocyclic monoterpenes, and to develop recommendations for studying their phytochemical composition[1,2].

Material and methods. Experiments Nurmatov Sh, et al., "Methods of Conducting Field Experiments" methodological manual. UzPITI.- Tashkent, 2007.- 146 was used.

Results and their analysis. Cappariaceae is a perennial herbaceous plant with a branchy, thorny, prostrate stem up to 2.5 m tall. The leaves are round, inverted ovate or elliptic, and are arranged in a row on the stem and branches with the help of bands. White, large, four-lobed flowers are located in the axils of the leaves with a long band. The fruit is multi-seeded, inverted egg-shaped, fluffy and looks like a wet fruit.

It blooms in May-June, the fruit ripens in July-August.

Geographic distribution. In Central Asia, Crimea, the Caucasus, it grows on roadsides, on hills, along railways, on dry banks of streams and canals, under walls, in dirty places, on hills, and sometimes in fields.

Applicable part. In folk medicine, the above-ground part, fruit, and root of kovull are used. The upper part of the ground and the fruit are collected when the plant blooms and dried in the shade. The flower is picked when it is in full bloom and the fruit is ripe. The flower is dried in the shade and the fruit is dried in the open air in the sun. washed in water, cleaned of soil and dried in the sun.

Phytochemical composition and use. The upper part of the fruit contains 0.32% rutin, quercetin up to 150 mg % vitamin C, stachydrin, thioglycoside, saponins, dyes, sugars in the fruit - up to 36%, 25-25.6 mg % vitamin C, 1.46 % flavanoids, thioglycoside; in seeds - 25-36% fat; in the root-1.2% alkaloids (stachydrine); There are 0.44% flavonoids, 4.5% sugar, coumarins and other substances.

Abu Ali ibn Sina used the plant of kowal for the treatment of shortness of breath, gastrointestinal diseases, and as a pain reliever, wound healer, and dewormer.

In folk medicine, a decoction made from the root is used to treat colds, paralysis, jaundice, kidney, and spleen diseases, and a decoction of the ground surface is used to treat gastrointestinal diseases, wounds, and asthma, and as a diuretic. The juice of the flower is used to treat sores and wounds, the decoction of the fruit is used to strengthen the gums, relieve toothache, cholera and other diseases.

Conclusions

Phytochemical composition of *Capparis spinosa* L. grown mainly in natural conditions. The surface part contains 0.32% rutin, quercetin up to 150 mg% vitamin C, stachydrin, thioglycoside, saponins, dyes, sugars in the fruit - up to 36%, 25-25.6 mg% vitamin C and other vitamins.

It was found in experiments on animals that root extract and decoction have the effect of accelerating blood clotting.

Considering *Capparis spinosa* L. plant as a popular plant today, we think that it would be appropriate to organize plantations of this promising medicinal plant in the hilly and steppe zones of our Republic and enrich the pharmaceutical industry with another natural medicine.

Figure 1. Flowering time of *Capparis spinosa* L. plant

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